

Identification and Monitoring of Pastures in Agroforestry using Multispectral Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Products

Introduction

Sown Biodiverse Pastures (SBP) are the basis of a high-yield grazing system tailored for Mediterranean ecosystems and widely implemented in Southern Portugal. The application of precision farming methods in SBP requires cost-effective monitoring using remote sensing (RS). The main hurdle for the remote monitoring of SBP is the fact that the bulk of the pastures are installed in open Montado agroforestry systems. Sparsely distributed trees cast shadows that hinder the identification of the underlying pasture using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) imagery. Image acquisition in the Spring is made difficult by the presence of flowers that mislead the classification algorithms. The project tested multiple procedures for the geographical, object-based image classification (GEOBIA) of SBP, aiming to reduce the effects of tree shadows and flowers in open Montado systems. It was used remotely sensed data acquired between November 2017 and May 2018 in three Portuguese farms. It was used three machine learning supervised classification algorithms: Random Forests (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). It was classified SBP based on:

- (1) a single-period image for the maximum Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) epoch in each of the three farms, and
- (2) multi-temporal image stacking. RF, SVM and ANN were trained using some visible (red, green and blue bands) and near-infrared (NIR) reflectance bands, plus NDVI and a Digital Surface Model (DSM).

It was obtained high overall accuracy and kappa index (higher than 79% and 0.60, respectively). The RF algorithm had the highest overall accuracy (more than 92%) for all farms. Multitemporal image classification increased the accuracy of the algorithms, as it helped to correctly identify as SBP the areas covered by tree shadows and flower patches, which would be misclassified using single image classification. This study thus established the first workflow for SBP monitoring based on remotely sensed data, suggesting an operational approach for SBP identification.

The workflow can be applied to other types of pastures in agroforestry regions to reduce the effects of shadows and flowering in classification problems.

Lessons learned

This study was performed to address an increasingly pressing need for RS-based classification of pastures in agroforestry regions, through the development of an accurate workflow capable of correctly

identifying pasture areas, even in the presence of trees shadows and flowers. Both effects confuse algorithms and lead to the underestimation of pasture areas using data collected on one singular date.

We showed here that a multitemporal approach is crucial in order to deal with the effects of tree shadows and flower patches. This approach works mostly due to the radiometric variability of SBP, compared to the trees and other objects in the ecosystem. To our knowledge, this was the first application of multitemporal classification that successfully decreased misclassifications due to shadows and flowers without requiring additional corrections. Prior approaches resorted to physical- or image-based correction methods to identify shadows or the application of multisource data fusion to fill shadowed areas. This study also applied for the first time GEOBIA classification and ML algorithms to identify SBP in Portugal. Although the type of ML algorithm made some difference, with RF being the most accurate, the most important methodological choice for obtaining accurate results was the use of multitemporal classification. The workflow presented here enables the identification of SBP area with an overall accuracy that is always higher than 79%, regardless of the approach.

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Figure 1. The drone used to capture multispectral data.

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Further information

<https://www.terraprima.pt/en/projecto/22>

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